

**APPROACHES TO RESOLVING THE "WOMEN'S QUESTION" IN CHARLOTTE BRONTË'S
NOVEL "SHIRLEY"**

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ABSTRACT

Charlotte Brontë's (1816-1855) novel "Shirley" (1849) is examined in this article as an important text for understanding the "woman question" in Victorian literature. One of the main goals of this article is to identify and analyze the main approaches to addressing women's status in society, as presented in the structure of the work. Particular attention is given to the characters of Caroline Helstone and Shirley Keeldar as bearers of different models of female identity and self-realization.

The article demonstrates that Charlotte Brontë offers several solutions to the woman question: through marriage as a socially acceptable form of self-realization; through financial independence and property ownership; and through the heroine's spiritual independence. Charlotte Brontë seeks to affirm the idea of moral and intellectual equality between women and men, while at the same time remaining within the traditional model of marriage, which is a key aspect of women's destiny. "Shirley" combines elements of social and psychological analysis, reflecting the influence of the historical context on the formation of gender roles. In conclusion, one can say that "Shirley" represents a transitional stage in the development of feminist thought: Brontë does not make a radical break with the patriarchal system, but rather lays the foundation for a further rethinking of the role of women in society.

Keywords: Shirley, Charlotte Brontë, women's issues, social role of women, Victorian literature.

Charlotte Brontë was a master of psychological realism, whose works are steeped in her personal life experiences. Her mature writing was shaped by the turbulent historical changes in England, which led to her choice of topical themes and her sympathetic tone towards the lives of ordinary people. The central theme of her novels is the journey of an independent and honest heroine. Combining traits of Brontë herself with her ideals of perfection, these heroines fearlessly resist their circumstances, becoming symbols of the struggle for inner freedom in an unjust world. The foundation of Charlotte Brontë's work was a spirit of protest, driven both by the writer's personal hardships and her deep awareness of the social injustices of the era towards women. A vivid embodiment of this stance was the novel "Shirley" (1849), published two years after the triumph of her first published novel, "Jane Eyre". The work was based on the historical events of the Luddite riots of the early 19th century, which served as a tool for the author to analyse the contemporary Chartist movements of the 1830s and 1840s. The famous politician and former Prime Minister Benjamin Disraeli succinctly characterised Britain of that period, noting that the country had effectively split into 'two nations' - the world of the haves and the world of the have-nots. [3, 350] This rigid class hierarchy not only divided people according to income level, but also served as an insurmountable barrier that strictly dictated a person's social status, determined the scope of their rights, and imposed severe limitations on their lives

Although the central plot conflict revolves around the dispute between the workers at the weaving mill and their employer, Moore, the most significant focus in "Shirley" is on the plight of women in a patriarchal society, as the title of the novel itself suggests. The plot of the novel is shaped by a dual love story: the relationship between the industrialist Robert Moore and the vicar's niece, Caroline Helstone, and the union between

the wealthy landowner Shirley Keeldar and the intellectual teacher Louis Moore. These romantic entanglements are inextricably linked to the social conflict at the heart of the work. In this way, Brontë sought to capture the genuine drama of human emotions unfolding against the harsh, and at times merciless, realities of everyday life. In Western literary studies, a common view - as expressed, for example, in H. Taylor's work [5, 84] - is that the central theme of "Shirley" is the phenomenon of social powerlessness. This motif unites the disparate plot lines: the oppressed position of women in a patriarchal society is analysed in parallel with the plight of the workers. In this way, Brontë draws a direct analogy between male domination and industrial exploitation, viewing them as two forms of the same systemic oppression.

At the heart of Brontë's exploration lies the contrast between two polarised female statuses: absolute subordination and financial independence. This is clearly evident in Chapter 10, where Caroline Helstone, having realised the illusory nature of the prospect of marriage, "asks herself the agonising question about the future of a single woman" [1, 180]: what is the meaning of life for a woman deprived of the traditional roles of wife and mother? In an attempt to find an answer to this existential question, Caroline visits two 'old maids' - Miss Mann and Miss Ainley. This encounter becomes a bitter revelation for her: she witnesses the fate of single women, whose unfulfilled dreams of personal happiness are met by society with nothing but irony or contempt. Through these characters, Brontë exposes the cruelty of a society that first deprives women of the opportunity to fulfil themselves outside the family, and then mocks them for their enforced solitude: 'The most cherished dream, the sole desire of each of them, is to get married, but most will never marry; they will die as they live. They all scheme, compete and dress up, trying to secure a husband for themselves. And the men

laugh at them... the market for brides is overflowing!" [1, 402].

The 'women's issue' in the novel is explored through a complex web of dialogues that represent a clash of opposing beliefs. Shirley and Caroline debate the priority of personal dignity and independence over the dubious benefits of an unhappy marriage. At the same time, Caroline's conversation with her mother, Mrs Prior, lays bare the conflict between romantic idealism and bitter scepticism. Brontë masterfully constructs a gender-based opposition: whilst Vicar Hall sees a woman's salvation in self-sacrificing service, male characters such as Mr Helstone and Joe Scott convey harsh patriarchal dogmas regarding the secondary nature of the female role. This entire spectrum of views—ranging from misogynistic outbursts to calls for emancipation—reflects the author's own inner struggle and her search for compromise within the contradictory social milieu of Victorian England.

Whilst in "Jane Eyre" the value of marriage as an ultimate goal is scarcely called into question (despite the variety of marital models depicted), in "Shirley" the author moves on to a more profound and critical analysis. Brontë dispassionately weighs up all the 'pros' and 'cons', assessing the advantages and hardships of both married life and forced or chosen solitude. The novel's ambivalent attitude towards female solitude is directly reflected in Brontë's private correspondence, where she constantly returns to this painful subject. Through the characters of Miss Mann and Miss Ainley, the author embodies the harsh realities of celibacy – isolation and the necessity of endless self-denial. Analysing their joyless fate, Caroline comes to a conclusion that echoes the writer's own position: '... a life of this sort, for all its purity and usefulness, condemned a person to loneliness; it did not warm them with love' [1. 189].

It must be acknowledged that, in her portrayals of elderly ladies, Brontë remains largely bound by established stereotypes. Thus, the psychological characterisation of Miss Mann bears clear traces of the caricature-like style characteristic of 18th-century English prose. By employing traditional techniques for depicting the 'old maid', the author unwittingly reproduces the literary tropes of a bygone era: '... to avoid any kind of excitement was Miss Mann's chief aim in life. From the very moment she came down from her bedroom, she tried to settle into a calm frame of mind and had already begun to sink into a pleasant half-sleep when a sudden knock at the door ruined everything' [1, 200]. The character of Miss Ainley, endowed with saintly traits and meekly enduring life's hardships, is also not free from clichés. In this case, Brontë resorts to a different type of stereotype—the sentimental portrayal of the 'old maid', which was widespread in the works of Victorian women writers. Here, the heroine is presented not as a caricature, but as an idealised example of humility and meekness.

Charlotte Brontë presents a far more optimistic view of the prospects for women's independence, as evidenced by her heroines who openly reject patriarchal marital ideology. The determination with which Shirley defends her individuality, and the self-sufficient, at times eccentric confidence of Hortense Moore, debunk the myth of the inevitable suffering of a single woman.

This stance is complemented by Rosa York's manifesto: in an argument with her mother, she asserts that female energy requires ample space for fulfilment, rather than the artificial constraints of the narrow confines of domestic life: 'I have decided that my life will be a real life... If the Creator has given me ten talents, it is my duty to put them all to work and double them all. I will not hide my talents in an old teapot and lock them away in the sideboard amongst the tea service. I will not wrap them in a woollen stocking to suffocate in your sewing table. Nor will I stow them away in the linen cupboard, where the sheets will become their shrouds' [1, 360]. Furthermore, Caroline and Shirley passionately criticise the stance of Helstone, who advocates keeping women away from active pursuits. Caroline's impassioned appeal to the men of England, in which she asks them to take notice of the pitiful state of their daughters, 'languishing from idleness', carries great significance in the novel: "Fathers! If you wish to take pride in your daughters rather than be ashamed of them, find them some useful occupation that will raise them above coquetry, intrigue and malicious gossip. If you stifle and restrict your daughters' minds, they will remain a thorn in your side and a burden, and at times even a source of shame. But if you educate them, give them freedom and a useful occupation, they will become your most cheerful companions whilst you are in good health, your most tender carers in times of illness, and your most faithful support in old age" [1, 389].

It is worth emphasising the profound ambivalence of Charlotte Brontë's stance on the institution of marriage in "Shirley". On the one hand, she debunks the illusion of marriage as the only path to happiness, likening it to a trap. Using the example of the daughters of the Simpson and Nunnley families, the author demonstrates the spiritual impoverishment of women whose interests are limited to an obsessive desire to marry. On the other hand, Brontë explores the destructive influence of an unhappy marriage on the individual: thus, Mrs York becomes embittered and harsh because of her union with a man who is deeply indifferent to her inner world. This tragic line-up is completed by Mrs Prior – yet another type of unhappy wife, whose life has become an example of agonising submission to unbearable circumstances. The novel's conclusion reveals Brontë's indecision regarding the ultimate liberation of women: the central issue remains unresolved. In contrast to the triumph of equality in "Jane Eyre", where the union of the protagonists harmonises gender opposition, the situation of Caroline and Shirley in the finale appears to be an artistic compromise. Their finding of husbands effectively signifies a return to the patriarchal hierarchy. Marriage here appears not as the crowning glory of freedom, but as bonds that once again place the heroines in a position of dependence, rendering the novel's ending ambiguous and at odds with its overall tone.

Such an ending stands in stark contrast to the passionate protest against gender restrictions that has been voiced throughout the novel. The dichotomy between the thirst for personal freedom and the social need for marriage is resolved in favour of the traditional canon of 'female happiness'. Nevertheless, the heroines' unions are not identical: they reflect the differences in

their psychological types. Whereas for Shirley marriage appears as a certain loss of autonomy, for Caroline it seems a natural conclusion, as her character and emotional needs fit entirely within the framework of 'traditional femininity' and the desire for a family home. To conclude this point and summarise the comparison of the two characters, the following options can be used, which highlight the difference between Rochester's spiritual rebirth and Moore's social pragmatism: Although Robert Moore, like Rochester, undergoes a journey of redemption and is reborn through suffering, he remains a proponent of the traditional view of the 'fairer sex': "Imagine that a single glance at her gentle countenance, a single thought of her, is enough for you to forget your anxieties and cares, to feel the purity of love, the charm of family life, and to be ready to exchange all the base, harsh calculations of a merchant for a kind word, for a selfless desire to love and protect her ..." [1, 553].

The metamorphosis undergone by the characters illustrates the artistic impasse into which Brontë finds herself: in order to fit Shirley into the framework of a Victorian ending, the author is forced to 'tame' her character. The transformation of the modest teacher Louis into a confident gentleman, and the simultaneous fading of Shirley's rebellious spirit, indicate that the ideal of equality to which the writer aspired proved unattainable within the social norms of the time. The heroine's final uncertainty serves as a subtle indication that this compromise was painful not only for the character, but also for the author herself. This doubt is likely due to the fact that her future husband avoids directly confirming their equality. Shirley's question: 'So, are we equal now? Equal at last?' [1, 641] – remains unanswered, transforming their union not into a partnership of equals, but into a covert form of domination and subjugation. It is difficult to dispute S. Foster's view regarding the thematic and psychological validity of Shirley and Louis's union [4, 101]. On the one hand, the heroine's worldview is not free from traditional ideals: she retains her faith in male nobility and consciously seeks a worthy companion. On the other hand, Shirley embodies the very duality of Brontë's authorial stance. The heroine paradoxically combines a zealous defence of her autonomy with a deep, purely human need for support and understanding."

To summarise the analysis of the novel "Shirley", it can be argued that this work served as a complex experiment for Charlotte Brontë in which she sought to intertwine social and gender discourses. By interweaving the historical backdrop of the Luddite riots with the 'women's issue', the author created a unique panorama of Victorian society, in which industrial exploitation and male domination are presented as related forms of systemic oppression. Brontë succeeded in moving beyond the confines of an individual love story, transforming the novel into a wide-ranging exploration of existential loneliness and a woman's quest for professional fulfilment outside traditional family roles.

The novel's central achievement is a profound deconstruction of the myth of the 'spinster' and 'women's happiness'. Through the tragic figures of Miss Mann and Miss Ainley, as well as through the impassioned appeals of Caroline Helstone, the author exposes the cruelty of a society that condemns women to intellectual and emotional decline. The contrast between passive waiting for marriage and an active pursuit of activity (Rose York's manifesto) underscores the progressive spirit of the work, in which female energy is viewed as a creative force in need of space, rather than the artificial confines of domestic life.

However, the novel's conclusion reveals a profound artistic and ideological divide. Despite the heroines' vigorous protest against patriarchal dogmas, their eventual marriage appears to be a reluctant compromise with the demands of literary tradition and the social norms of the era.

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